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Acronyms and abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board	HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
ABL	Advanced Bioenergy Lab	IS	Industrial Symbiosis
BFG	Bubbling Fluidized Bed (gasifier)	LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure	MeOH	Methanol
CBM	Circular Business Model	MW	Megawatt
CCU	Carbon Capture and Utilization	NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
CE	Circular Economy	RDF	Refuse-Derived Fuel
CRM	Critical Raw Material	SN	Stakeholder Network
DFB	Dual Fluidized Bed Gasifier	SOC	Solid Oxide Cell
EC	European Commission	SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell
EIS	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy	SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
EUBCE	European Biomass Conference and Exhibition	TRL	Technology Readiness Level
		WP	Work Package

Acronyms used to identify consortium members

ECODESIGN	ECODESIGN company engineering & management consultancy GmbH
ELCOGEN	Elcogen OY
EUCORE	EU CORE Consulting s.r.l
ICODOS	ICODOS GmbH
LUT	LAPPEENRANNAN-LAHDEN TEKNILLINEN YLIOPISTO LUT
UNI	Italian National Standardization Body (Ente Italiano di Normazione)
VTT	TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY

1. Publishable executive summary

The BeBOP project is developing a novel Bio/e-Methanol production process combining biomass gasification with Solid Oxide Cell (SOC) technology, and demonstrates it within a TRL6 pilot plant. The core goal is to provide a substitute process based on renewables (both biomass and energy) for a fossil-based one (mostly natural gas). Therefore, ensuring that circularity principles are integrated from the earliest design stages is essential.

This deliverable is the second report documenting the results of the Work Package (WP4), fully dedicated to Circularity in this project. It presents the main outputs of the circularity assessment conducted across six targeted Circularity Workshops and one Joint Workshop with strong stakeholders' engagement, completed between January and December 2025.

Building on the methodological framework presented in the previous report (D4.1) *Tailored methods and impactful tools for boosting BeBOP circularity opportunities*, the assessment applies four circular economy (CE) principles to the BeBOP life cycle: **i)** Narrowing (using fewer resources), **ii)** Slowing (extending component lifetimes), **iii)** Closing (creating material and energy loops), and **iv)** Regenerating (using renewable and non-toxic inputs). The BeBOP technical experts (Consortium partners), Advisory Board and broader Stakeholders' Network members contributed to the assessment.

A central output of the assessment is the **BeBOP Circularity Indicator Set**: 25 quantitative indicators across four life cycle stages – including feedstock selection and pre-treatment, gasification and gas cleaning, SOEC/SOFC operation and methanol synthesis - were proposed and further discussed for their suitability. More concretely, each indicator was selected based on its relevance to scale-up decisions and the feasibility of data gathering or direct measurements. Key Circularity indicators include the SOEC Stack Degradation Rate, the Cold Gas Efficiency of the gasifier, the Heat Reuse Efficiency, the Secondary Source Index and the Marginal Land Source Index. The indicators are process-specific by design, reflecting the unique characteristics of the BeBOP technology rather than generic circularity metrics.

A systematic interdependency analysis revealed that some of the circularity indicators have inherent trade-offs. The most critical trade-off is between feedstock flexibility and both process performance and SOEC longevity. A second significant trade-off exists between maximizing renewable electricity use and system stability, as intermittent supply causes thermal cycling that shortens SOEC stack lifetime. On the other hand, heat integration is a predominantly synergistic area: improvements in heat reuse benefit multiple circularity objectives simultaneously and carry few negative trade-offs. These findings confirm that BeBOP circularity optimization is a multi-objective problem requiring system-level solutions.

Based on the full assessment, four key recommendations are made for a long-term 100 MW commercial BeBOP scale-up: design for SOC longevity, build heat integration into the plant concept from the start, choose plant location strategically to maximize industrial symbiosis, and prioritize feedstock quality (in terms of a preferably low ash and impurity content) as a system-wide circularity lever. The indicators, trade-off matrix and circular business model scenarios developed in this WP will feed directly into the Life Cycle Assessment and the techno-economic analysis, and into the exploitation activities, especially the business cases for BeBOP.

2. Introduction: The imperative for circularity in BeBOP

The transition toward sustainable chemical production requires a fundamental rethinking of how industrial processes are designed, operated and integrated within broader industrial ecosystems. The BeBOP project addresses this requirement by developing a hybrid Methanol production process that combines biomass gasification with Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell (SOC) technology. The SOC enables two key innovations: a high Carbon efficiency via co-electrolysis with the syngas (SOEC) and the flexibility to transform syngas from gasification into electricity in fuel-cell mode (SOFC).

However, as the BeBOP process competes with other green Methanol pathways, the long-term viability and environmental performance of the technology depend critically on how circularity principles are embedded from the earliest design stages. This is particularly relevant given that the project targets scale-up to a 100MW commercial plant in the long term, where decisions made during pilot development (TRL 6) could have lasting implications for resource efficiency, component longevity and industrial symbiosis opportunities.

The concept of Circular Economy (CE) provides a systematic framework for optimizing resource flows throughout the technology's life cycle. As established in previous work (D4.1 Tailored Methods and Impactful Tools for Boosting BeBOP Circularity Opportunities) the BeBOP approach to circularity is based on four core principles (Bocken et al. 2016): **i)** Narrowing (using fewer resources); **ii)** Slowing (extending product and component lifespans); **iii)** Closing (creating material and energy loops); and **iv)** Regenerating (utilizing renewable and non-toxic resources). These principles also align with emerging European sustainability reporting standards and voluntary assessment frameworks such as Circulytics and the Circular Transition Indicators

This Deliverable builds upon the methodological foundation established (Schmidt et al. 2025) by presenting the results of a comprehensive circularity assessment conducted through stakeholder-engaged workshops. The assessment aims to identify the most critical variables for maximizing circularity in a scaled-up BeBOP plant. By involving technical experts from across the consortium as well as external stakeholders from the Advisory Board and Stakeholder Network, the workshops ensured that circularity strategies are both technically feasible and aligned with industrial practice.

The structure of this report reflects the progression of work from identifying and describing qualitative circularity strategies, to the development of quantitative performance indicators. Chapter 3 describes the methodological approach and stakeholder integration mechanisms. Chapter 4 presents the main results: the application of circularity strategies across the BeBOP life cycle (§4.1), the validation of these strategies through workshop discussions (§4.2), the derivation of quantitative indicators including trade-off analysis (§4.3) and the exploration of circular business model opportunities (§4.4). Finally, Chapter 5 provides recommendations for the BeBOP scale-up and discusses the integration of results within upcoming work packages.

The validated circularity indicators presented in this report provide the foundation for informed decision-making as the BeBOP technology advances toward commercial deployment.

3. Methodology and Stakeholder Integration

3.1. Methodological Approach

The circularity assessment for the BeBOP project follows a structured, stakeholder-engaged methodology designed to translate high-level circular economy principles into quantifiable indicators for a scaled-up Methanol production plant. The methodology consists of four interconnected phases: strategic framing, collaborative validation, indicator quantification and interdependency analysis.

The strategic framing phase established the foundation by mapping the four CE principles – i.e., narrowing, slowing, closing and regenerating - onto the specific life cycle stages of the BeBOP process, as documented in the previous deliverable of this work package (D4.1). Each life cycle stage (feedstock selection and pre-treatment, gasification and cleaning, SOEC/SOFC operation, methanol synthesis and product use) presents distinct circularity opportunities and challenges. This mapping produced a comprehensive set of research themes and questions, organized according to CE principles, shaping the content for the structured workshop discussions.

The collaborative validation phase operationalized this framework through seven targeted circularity workshops conducted between January 2025 and December 2025. The sequential approach of the workshops and the associated life cycle stages are shown in Figure 1, and hereby described in more detail:

- Workshop 1 (held on February 26th, 2025 at VTT, Espoo) addressed gasification, cooling and cleaning systems
- Workshop 2 (held on April 10th, 2025 at Elcogen, Vantaa) examined the integration and the reversibility of SOEC/SOFC
- Workshop 3 (held on April 30th, 2025 at Güssing Energy technologies, Güssing) explored biomass feedstock selection and pre-treatment
- Workshop 4 (held on May 21st, 2025 at Icodos, Mannheim) investigated the methanol synthesis unit, including the 3D-printed reactor design.
- Workshop 5 (held on June 18th 2025, online) engaged participants in translating the validated circularity strategies into measurable performance indicators
- Workshop 6 (held on October 9th, 2025 at UNI, Milano) focused on Circular Business Model Opportunities for pre-commercial demonstration.
- Workshop 7 (held on December 5th, 2025 online) was a Joint Workshop with the EU Project UNITED CIRCLES and standardization experts from UNI.

Each workshop brought together technical experts responsible for the respective process units with environmental engineers from ECODESIGN company, ensuring that discussions were grounded in both technical feasibility and CE principles or circularity strategies (these terms are used interchangeably).

Figure 1. Progression of the methodology along the life cycle stages.

The first 4 workshop sessions followed a similar three-part structure:

1. An introduction to circular economy concepts and their relevance and applicability to the specific life cycle stage;
2. A more detailed presentations about the technology under investigation;
3. A moderated group discussion of pre-defined research questions related to the CE principles, to synthesize qualitative levers for circularity.

The pre-defined discussion topics ensured systematic coverage of critical issues (such as resource efficiency, feedstock flexibility, component lifetime, etc.). At the same time, the workshops maintained sufficient flexibility to allow participants to explore topics of particular relevance, or to identify new circularity levers not anticipated in the initial framing.

Workshop 5 enabled a transition point in the methodology, shifting focus from qualitative strategy to exploring the definitions and the quantification of circularity indicators. This workshop engaged participants in translating the validated circularity strategies into measurable performance indicators. Through structured group work, the participants evaluated potential indicators based on criteria such as relevance for the scale-up of BeBOP and alignment with industry practice (“relevance”) and measurability (“feasibility”) of the indicators. This process resulted in the BeBOP Circularity Indicator Set, comprising 25 indicators across the four core life cycle stages: **(1)** Feedstock selection and pre-treatment, **(2)** Gasification and gas cleaning, **(3)** SOEC/SOFC operation and **(4)** Methanol Synthesis. Indicators were further refined after Workshop 5. This also involved an analysis of indicator interdependencies. This phase revealed that certain circularity indicators exhibit inherent trade-offs and synergies. These are systematically analyzed in Section 4.3.2.

Workshop 6 took a complementary approach by exploring how circular business models could enable the realization of circularity potentials identified in earlier workshops. Using scenario analysis, participants examined two possible, contrasting business model archetypes: 'Plug and Play Methanol' emphasizing distributed, modular deployment of the BeBOP concept, and 'The Eternal SOC', focusing on the component longevity through performance contracting and refurbishment services. The deeper analysis and discussion of these scenarios helped identify the enabling conditions and the barriers for the implementation of a circular business model, particularly in the phase of small-scale pre-commercial application after the completion of the BeBOP project.

The workshop series was concluded with Workshop 7, which brought together various stakeholders to compare circularity frameworks and discuss further implementation. The workshop was co-organized with the Horizon Europe project [UNITED CIRCLES](#) - an industrial-urban symbiosis project building regional Hubs for Circularity across multiple countries and value chains. Also participating were

members of the committee CEN/TC 473 on “Circular Economy”, introducing the Italian standard UNI/TS 11820:2024. This is currently the only European normative document for measuring organizational circularity, using 68 indicators across six categories. The main finding was that circularity frameworks must be tailored to their context (EU CORE Consulting s.r.l et al. 2025) - a low-TRL process innovation like BeBOP requires different indicators than an established organization or a large-scale symbiosis network. This further underlined and validated the methodology described here.

Rather than applying generic circularity metrics (as already identified in Schmidt et al. 2025), this assessment developed indicators tailored to the specific characteristics of the BeBOP technologies, to enhance the utility of the indicators for informing design decisions, and for benchmarking performance as the technology matures.

The methodology depended on the expertise of stakeholders, such as chemical engineers and industrial practitioners. These stakeholders can be structured in three different groups: The project consortium members (“internal stakeholders”), the Advisory Board (external stakeholders involved in the project) and the Stakeholder Network (external experts recruited throughout the project). The following section goes into the process of their selection, engagement and involvement.

3.2. Purpose and role of the Advisory Board and Stakeholder Network

The Advisory Board (AB) and the Stakeholders’ Network (SN) were strategically established as complementary external governance mechanisms aimed at strengthening the industrial relevance and the exploitation potential of the BeBOP project, and for promoting market uptake, ensuring alignment with industrial needs, policy developments and EU strategies.

The AB gathers high-level experts representing key domains such as Methanol industry deployment, policy and regulatory frameworks, circular economy strategies and industrial decarbonization as depicted in **Table 1**. In addition to provide independent advice on project implementation, its role is to support the consortium in positioning the BeBOP concept within broader European innovation ecosystems.

	AB member	Affiliation	Expertise domain
1	Alexander DÖLL	Methanol Institute	Methanol industry deployment
2	Jenő KOVÁCS	Sumitomo SHI-FW	Industrial decarbonization
3	Anastasios PERIMENIS	CO ₂ Value Europe	Policy and regulatory frameworks for CCU technologies
4	Margarita DE GREGORIO	BIOPLAT, Spanish Alliance for Sustainable Air Transport	Circular economy strategies
5	Iker GARCIA	ECOMOSA	Circular economy strategies

Table 1. BeBOP Advisory Board Members

In parallel, the Stakeholders’ Network was designed as a broader external expert community involving, as shown in **Table 2**, end-users, value-chain representatives, research organizations and policymakers’ actors. The SN supports the Scientific Group by providing technical and strategic feedback on the quality and relevance of project activities, the feasibility of circularity approaches and potential pathways for industrial adoption.

	SN Member	Affiliation	Expertise domain
1	Giuseppe BONURA	CNR ITAE in Messina	Research and value chain.
2	Ralf DIEMER	eFuel Alliance e.V	Policymaking: Climate and Environment
3	Anna KOCYK	ORLEN S.A	Biopolymers and biochemicals.

	SN Member	Affiliation	Expertise domain
4	Michał KOTOWICZ	ORLEN S.A	CCU technologies, with a focus on upscaling.
5	Marcin WALTER ¹	ORLEN S.A	Petroleum technology and CO ₂ management.
6	Gaulicia MENDES SOUZA	University of São Paulo	Molecular biology and sustainability assessment - Academia and Research.
7	Marco UGOLINI	Care For Engineering (CFE)	Association focused on environmental sustainability.
8	Jouni HAVUKAINEN	LUT University	Environmental sustainability of energy systems - Academia and Research.

Table 2. BeBOP Stakeholders' Network Members

Both boards operate on a voluntary basis and, during the first project reporting period, were actively involved in the circularity workshops.

3.3. Selection and engagement of the Stakeholders

The selection and mobilization of stakeholders followed a structured methodology. A preliminary analysis was conducted by project partner EUCORE, to identify first the relevant technological ecosystems and then the relevant stakeholder categories aligned with the value chain and circularity objectives of BeBOP. This process resulted in the identification of various stakeholder groups, including technology providers, end-users, value-chain representatives, industry associations, environmental organizations, authorities / policymakers, research communities, and think tanks. Stakeholders' profiles were then sought first among BeBOP partner's network. This approach minimized the risk of conflict of interest with project partners, and ensured an efficient and effective establishment of stable contacts. The composition of both boards is not intended to be static; there will be the possibility of integrating additional experts identified along the project duration, for example, during conferences, trade fairs, clustering activities, and through dedicated services such as the Horizon Results Booster (add-on service).

A mapping matrix was created to highlight expertise profiles, expected roles and engagement potential of each board member, thus supporting in defining the importance of each of these stakeholders for the project, and to maximize his/her involvement in targeted initiatives. This approach supported in fact targeted invitations and ensured balanced representation across different fields of expertise. Legal arrangements, including Non-disclosure Agreements (NDAs), were implemented to protect intellectual property and favor mutual exchanges of information.

3.4. Feedback of the Stakeholders to the BeBOP circularity workshops

Stakeholders' feedback was regularly collected through structured pre- and post-workshop questionnaires distributed to the Advisory Board and the Stakeholders' Network members who were participating in the BeBOP circularity workshops and joint event. The questionnaires mainly aimed to assess:

¹ Marcin Walter has been part of the network until March 2026, and activities for his substitution are already in place.

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- The perceptions of the technological relevance of BeBOP
- The expectations and usefulness of the activities in which the stakeholders were involved
- The insights and recommendations to improve the project activities and its impact.

The questionnaires included a scope up to 5 points for high level of satisfaction. Overall, the Circularity workshops received very positive evaluations. Participants reported that expectations were largely met, and highlighted the value of interactive discussions and project showcases, particularly when comparing BeBOP with complementary initiatives such as UNITED CIRCLES. The joint event with UNITED CIRCLES, in particular, was an important occasion to discuss industrial symbiosis at various levels, and the applicability of circular economy standards in real industrial contexts. This Joint Workshop achieved high satisfaction scores, with overall evaluation ratings exceeding 4.5 out of 5 points, and a strong appreciation for the effectiveness of the presenters and the practical relevance of the discussions.

From a technical perspective, the first six circularity workshops were aimed at assessing the circularity of the main value-chain technologies of the BeBOP process. Thus, based on the different areas of interest of the external experts within the workshop, the most interesting feedback concerned the following:

- The importance of reducing CAPEX and operational complexity
- The need for clear sustainability criteria and harmonized certification frameworks
- The importance of cultural acceptance of residual valorization for the uptake of circular solution
- The relevance of integrating standardization activities early in the innovation life cycle as a key enabler for market uptake.

Feedback from the stakeholders also highlighted several challenges of the BeBOP concept, including the importance of addressing the integration and combination of gasification and advanced electrolysis technologies within existing industrial infrastructures, as well as regulatory and permitting barriers, particularly in relation to biomass residue classification. Some stakeholders highlighted cultural and knowledge barriers affecting the acceptance of residue valorization approaches, suggesting that demonstration activities and stakeholder engagement remain critical to overcoming these obstacles.

The participants of the AB and SN greatly contributed with their views on circularity and performance indicators and their relevance from an industrial perspective.

Participants expressed interest in further involvement in project activities, and requested continued updates on developments, demonstrating the effectiveness of the engagement strategy in building a committed BeBOP stakeholder community. The feedback collected so far is useful both for the technical development and for the exploitation activities.

After detailing the methodology for the Circularity Assessment and how different stakeholder groups were involved in this process, the following chapter describes the continued evolution of results.

4. Results

This chapter describes the evolution of activities and corresponding results, starting from the identification and description of the circularity strategies for the BeBOP technologies and their integration, all the way to the final analysis of trade-offs for the specific, quantitative circularity indicators. As the BeBOP process integrates various technologies into a new concept, the knowledge and expertise are often siloed in specific domains. However, the successful integration of the technology elements is highly dependent on a systems perspective. The framework of the CE strategies enables this system's perspective view, by “zooming out” and investigating interdependencies. The chapter is structured in five sections, and along the CE principles of “Narrowing”, “Slowing”, “Closing” and “Regenerating”, as follows: §4.1. Applying CE strategies to BeBOP; §4.2 From CE strategies to validation; §4.3 From validated CE strategies to quantitative Circularity Indicators; §4.4. Interdependencies of Circularity Indicators; §4.5 Identifying circular business model opportunities.

4.1. Applying CE strategies to BeBOP

To systematically address circularity across the BeBOP value chain, the content of the workshops was planned and structured along the life cycle stages of BeBOP, with each workshop tackling the specific circularity challenges and opportunities relevant to that technology domain.

These discussion topics served as guiding frameworks rather than rigid constraints. The format of the workshops allowed for flexibility to explore emerging themes, and to prioritize topics, based on participants' expertise and the perceived relevance to the scale-up of BeBOP. Each workshop has been separately documented within their own reports providing the basis for most of the results. These reports are only available internally and to the stakeholders involved and are listed in the sources. Table 3 to follow presents an overview of the diverse and numerous workshop topics, framed for discussion with respect to the four CE principles.

“Narrowing” focuses on resource and energy efficiency improvements. For the BeBOP process, this translates primarily into optimizing the energy-intensive SOEC operation (responsible for approximately 90% of the overall electricity demand (Rajaei et al. 2024)), maximizing Carbon conversion efficiency in the gasifier and Methanol synthesis unit and minimizing energy requirements for biomass pre-treatment. Topics focused on the influences on these efficiencies, also across the value chain, e.g., how SOFC mode (electricity generation from syngas during high price periods) influences downstream methanol synthesis. Apart from process improvements “Narrowing” is particularly relevant in relation to critical raw materials such as those in the SOCs, to improve their potential availability over time, and to develop alternative, substitution materials.

“Slowing” strategies aim to extend the operational lifetime and utilization of process equipment and components. Given the capital-intensive nature of industry assets, especially of the SOC infrastructure, prolonging asset lifespans directly impacts economic viability and reduces embodied environmental burdens from equipment manufacturing and replacement. For BeBOP, potential slowing levers therefore require a deep understanding of the process conditions and the targeted feedstock flexibility which influence the service life of components. Another focus was set on the potential to prolong the life-time either pre-emptively (through strategies such as modular design, maintenance, digital twin monitoring) or in response to failures (e.g. optimization for repair or component exchange). As an example this includes the optimal design of the Methanol synthesis unit for a fast and safe catalyst exchange, minimizing plant downtime.

“Closing” strategies are about keeping material and energy in cycles or loops. Applied to BeBOP these potentials exist, both within the process itself and with other facilities through industrial symbiosis. The high-temperature nature of processes in the BeBOP concept indicate that heat recovery opportunities

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shall be further explored for their full integration. On the material level, “closing” the loops would be possible for water from the Methanol synthesis condensate, for Oxygen from the SOEC to support gasification, and for the solid residues (Biochar/ash) through their valorization for agricultural or construction applications. “Closing” addresses the end-of-life of the process consumables (such as catalysts and cleaning agents), as well as the industrial equipment itself.

“**Regenerating**” focuses on using renewable, non-toxic resources which shall be safely returned to the biosphere. For BeBOP, this means the preferred use of renewable energy and biomass inputs, but both entail certain complexity. The intermittent supply from renewable energy is anticipated by the BeBOP process design - during periods of high prices (Low renewable supply) BeBOP can switch to electricity generation via SOFC mode. This switching capacity requires the integration of buffer storage (batteries, Syngas, Hydrogen). Secondly, BeBOP aims to operate flexibly with a variety of secondary feedstocks, realizing cascading potentials and minimizing the growing usage competition for primary biomass, but again causing trade-offs due to increased complexity of process operation.

Overview of the discussion topics addressed during the Circularity Workshops 1 to 4.				
CE Strategy	Feedstock Selection and Pre-treatment	Gasification and Cleaning	SOC	Methanol Synthesis
 Narrow	The role of pre-treatment in overall costs and efficiency influences	Factors influencing gasification and cleaning efficiency (i.e., heat recovery, temperature management).	Availability and substitutability of Critical Raw Materials used in SOCs.	Implications of scaling-up 3D-printed reactor designs (sizing vs. Multiplication).
		Monitoring efficiency with sensor networks and digital twins.	Understanding optimal operating condition variables to reduce energy demand.	Maintaining advantages of process intensification due to 3D-printed designs at scale.
		Internal heat reutilization potential.	Conditions for switching to SOFC mode and its impacts on downstream processes	Flexibility of load conditions to reduce potential buffer storage needs.
 Slow	Feedstocks and their impact on process performance (impurities, moisture).	Modularity potentials and design for maintenance, repair and upgrades.	Design Optimization for Capital Expenditures vs. Operational Expenditures.	Influences on the service life of catalysts (heat management, syngas quality, load).
		Availability of critical spare parts.	Typical lifetime of SOC components and the main factors influencing it	Reactor design to improve/hinder catalyst loading and unloading
		Predictability and Detectability of wear and degradation	Heterogeneity of cell degradation and the smallest exchangeable unit.	Reactor durability and maintenance needs.
		Consequences of Shutdowns and factors to minimize downtimes.	Maintenance and repairability potentials.	Monitoring techniques to prolong service life.
		Influences on the lifetime of components, such as corrosion and ash deposits.		
 Close	Integration of biomass use within local and regional economies (Industrial Symbiosis).	Use of waste streams from other industries as feedstocks.	Feasibility of closed-loop business models (refurbishment and recycling).	Heat reuse potentials from exothermic reaction.
		Composition and quantity of waste streams (ash, char, sorbents, etc).	Challenges in recovering and recycling key materials from decommissioned stacks.	Water reutilization and the goal of net-zero water discharge.
		Potential revalorization routes for waste streams		Concepts for spent catalyst recycling
		Optimal plant location for industrial symbiosis.	Use of internal resource streams from (oxygen) or for SOC (waste heat, water).	End-of-life routes for the reactor and recoverability of high-value metal alloys.
		Recyclability of industrial components at end of life.		
 Regenerate	Feedstock selection criteria (quality, supply, stability, cost, usage competition, etc.) Viable future feedstocks for large-scale gasification	Gasifier adaptability to different biomass feedstocks.	Influence of plant location to renewable energy systems.	Adaptability of MeOH Synthesis to SOFC use case (low syngas loads).
		Trade-offs between feedstock flexibility and operational complexity.	Feasibility of process adaptation to intermittent renewables.	Conditions under which buffer storages for syngas or hydrogen are needed.
		Definition of "biomass families" with similar characteristics.	Need for buffer storage (hydrogen or battery) for intermittent renewable electricity supply.	

Table 3. Overview of discussion topics addressed during the Circularity Workshops 1 to 4.

4.2. From CE strategies to validation

The workshop's discussions translated the Circular Economy framework into concrete, validated insights, specific to the circularity potential for the scale-up of the BeBOP technology. Similar to the previous sections, the findings are structured along the four CE principles, and are summarized in Table 4. The following sections describe the validated CE strategies.

4.2.1. "Narrowing" strategies: Enhancing process and resource efficiency

The (CE) principle of "Narrowing" concentrates on using less energy and material per unit of output, which is important across all life cycle stages, although with notably different leverage points at each technology component in BeBOP.

A central finding is the relationship **between feedstock flexibility and process efficiency**. The most resource-efficient outcome would be to minimize energy losses and auxiliary consumption throughout the conversion chain - feedstock quality is the most important upstream parameter for reaching this outcome. Clean woody biomass consistently delivers the highest cold gas efficiency, and the lowest gas cleaning load. Clean wood has a relatively homogeneous composition which yields stable syngas, with low tar content and manageable ash behavior. **Secondary biomass sources**, such as agricultural residues, refuse-derived fuels (RDFs) and forestry residues, typically **introduce higher concentrations of impurities** such as sulphur, chlorine and heavy metals, as well as low ash-melting-point constituents, increasing the risk of bed agglomeration and downstream fouling. These negative effects increase the intensity of cleaning, raise auxiliary energy demand, and often reduce (annual) operating hours.

Workshop participants emphasized that the true cost of low-quality feedstock is reflected in the indirect operational consequences, ultimately leading to a reduced plant uptime. Nevertheless, secondary biomass and feedstocks from agricultural and forest residues remain strategically important, both for economic reasons and for their lower usage competition with other use cases. Optimizing their use within acceptable quality boundaries represents a challenge for a future BeBOP plant design and operation.

At the **gasification stage**, both internal and external **heat reutilizations** were identified as the most significant lever for "Narrowing", enabling also a synergy with the operation of the SOC. Heat recovered from Syngas cooling, both during gas cleaning and after the SOC, can be redirected to steam generation, substantially reducing the external energy input. The tight integration between the gasifier and the SOC is essential to minimize energy losses.

The **incorporation of sensor networks for real-time monitoring** of gas composition, temperature and impurity levels, together with predictive maintenance strategies underpinned by process digital twins, was identified as a promising means of maintaining optimal operating conditions and detecting efficiency losses early. A digital twin of the pilot-scale plant will already be developed within the project lifetime.

Within the **SOC**, the primary "Narrowing" focus relates to the **use and potential substitution of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs)**. The main materials in the SOC stacks by weight are ferritic steels (containing iron and Chromium), as well as Nickel, Zirconium and Yttrium in the unit cells. Nickel and Zirconium each account for roughly 50% of solid oxide cell materials and are currently considered irreplaceable given their electrochemical function. Zirconium and Yttrium are not presently on the EU CRM list while Nickel's classification may evolve depending on its sourcing geography (Regulation (EU) 2024/1252). Other CRMs - including Cobalt, Lanthanum, Scandium, Cerium and Gadolinium are used in very small quantities at the SOC cells. Cobalt in particular is the subject of active research by BeBOP partner ELCOGEN, with a credible pathway for its substitution in protective coatings within a few years.

At the Methanol synthesis, the **3D-printed reactor technology introduces significant "Narrowing" opportunities through process intensification**. The optimized internal geometry of the reactor provides superior heat transfer and thermal control, which are essential for the exothermic Methanol

synthesis reaction. The reactor is designed to operate dynamically across a range of 25 to 100% of its nominal capacity, reducing the need for large upstream buffer storage systems (for Hydrogen or Syngas), and enabling the whole plant to adapt to variable renewable electricity supply with minimal resource waste. However, for the plant scale-up, it still remains unclear if the 3D-printed design would be viable due to the limitations of 3D manufacturing for larger reactor sizes. It was estimated that the size could scale-up to approximately 20 to 40 times the pilot reactor volume. Further scale-up would require multiplication of reactor units, and parallel processing of the Syngas.

4.2.2. “Slowing” strategies: Extending asset and component lifetimes

The “Slowing” principle aims at keeping components and infrastructure operational for as long as possible. This emerged as a highly impactful CE principle for the BeBOP concept, particularly for the capital-intensive SOC unit. Workshops’ findings consistently highlighted that component lifetime and design for proper maintenance are among the primary determinants of economic viability.

Even if “Slowing” strategies are less directly applicable to feedstock supply chains, it became apparent that **feedstock quality has a significant indirect effect on the lifetime** of components. Higher impurity content in the feedstock would accelerate the degradation of gas cleaning absorbents, increase the risk of corrosion in the gasifier and heat exchangers, and significantly reduce the useful life of the sensitive SOC stack due to poisoning from the impurities. A feedstock strategy that prioritizes consistent and predictable quality is also a “Slowing” strategy to protect the longevity of expensive process equipment.

At the **gasification stage, “Slowing” deals with the management of corrosion, ash deposits and minimizing the unplanned shutdowns**. Ash composition and bed material choice (e.g., olivine) are important variables: certain contaminants, such as Chrome-6 leached from bed materials, can limit the reuse of ash in agriculture, and may affect downstream components. The ability to detect and anticipate wear and degradation, through regular maintenance intervals and component lifetime data into a digital twin, was highlighted as a promising approach to maximize plant uptime, and to reduce the frequency and the cost of maintenance interventions.

Finally, Syngas purification units were identified as potential candidates for modular upgrade designs, with two-parallel-reactor configurations (one in capture mode, one in regeneration) enabling adsorbent recovery during operation without a full shutdown.

The detailed finding from the workshop about the SOC, reflect the importance of the **SOC as the component with the highest cost impact** over the plant's operational life. The current stack lifetime is estimated up to 5 years, with a replacement cost of around 200 EUR/kW, compared to an overall system cost of approximately 1,500 EUR/kW (or future target costs of 300–400 EUR/kW). The most valuable “Slowing” strategies shall extend the lifetime of the stacks, and reduce their replacement frequency. Four primary degradation mechanisms of the SOC were identified: impurity poisoning by Sulphur and tars (damaging electrochemically active sites); Carbon formation (coking), which can mechanically destroy the SOC cell structure; Nickel depletion and migration in the fuel electrode, particularly during co-electrolysis; and increased internal resistance accumulating over time. Impurity poisoning and Carbon formation were considered the most operationally significant mechanisms of degradation, but at the same time, these are amenable to mitigation through rigorous upstream gas cleaning. Degradation is furthermore heterogeneous within a (SOC) module: stacks at the edges of an assembly experience greater heat loss and different gas compositions than those in the center, an effect that must be managed through careful flow distribution and thermal design.

The **smallest unit that could be replaced in a SOC assembly is an individual stack** (currently 200 kW, with 400 kW targeted for future systems). Refurbishment of degraded cells or stacks is not considered technically feasible at this time due to the irreversible material changes such as diffusion, sintering, and chromium depletion. Module replacement and material recycling are, therefore, the viable end-of-life pathway at this time. Advanced monitoring strategies for voltage, current, temperature and pressure offer the most practical route to extending the useful operational life of the SOC. Direct electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was noted as a technique to localize degradation, and localized monitoring within modules also helps identifying cold spots prone to Carbon formation, or hot spots accelerating degradation. Another strategy is to deliberately operate cells at “milder” conditions, trading in short-term efficiency (narrowing) for a longer lifetime (slowing).

For the Methanol synthesis unit, the **catalyst management is of particularly high relevance**. Its service life is conservatively estimated at two to three years, with the primary degradation mechanism is localized overheating that causes sintering of active catalyst sites. The contaminants in the Syngas can also poison the catalyst bed. The high purity demand of the SOC upstream, provides a meaningful synergy in that regard. Furthermore, the optimized internal geometry of the 3D-printed reactor, supported by a dense network of temperature sensors throughout the catalyst bed provide superior heat distribution, prevents hot spot formation and enables operation closer to the catalyst's thermodynamic optimum.

Controlled start-up and shutdown procedures, achievable within approximately one hour for the 3D-printed reactor (compared to around eight hours for conventional reactors), further reduce thermal cycling stress on the catalyst.

As a counterpart, the **catalyst exchange itself requires approximately two weeks of non-productive time** per reactor. This process encompasses a one-week oxidation passivation of the spent catalyst before unloading, two to three days for the physical exchange, and a further week-long reduction process to activate the fresh, new catalyst bed. Coordinating this sequence using hot-standby modules or planned maintenance windows is therefore an important operational strategy. The reactor housing itself is designed for a service life of 10 to 20 years, broadly comparable to conventional pressure equipment.

4.2.3. “Closing” strategies: Creating loops for materials, wastes and heat

The “Closing” principle looks after keeping materials and energy within productive loops. There were many opportunities identified across the BeBOP value chain, for heat integration, water cycling and recovery of materials.

The **most significant opportunity at the gasification stage is heat recovery**. Heat from Syngas cooling (During gas cleaning and after the SOC), and heat from Syngas compression can be redirected to generate steam, which in turn is used as the gasification agent, substantially closing the energy loop at the process level. There is also a significant opportunity to use waste heat for district heating, e.g. as done at the Austrian biomass plant in Güssing. The workshop on gasification further confirmed that the entire water balance of the BeBOP process could be managed as a **closed system, targeting zero discharge**. The moisture from the input biomass, the steam used as the gasification agent and the condensate recovered during Syngas cooling, compression and methanol distillation could be collected, treated and recycled to cover the steam demand of the gasifier and the syngas conditioning steps. However, the treatment step is key because the processes require ultra-pure water, adding practical challenges to the realization of this potential.

The solid waste streams, primarily ash, char, sorbents and bed materials, represent a more complex challenge for closing the loop. Biochar from clean biomass sources may be valorized in soil applications, as long as the impurity levels remain within regulatory bounds. For biomass sources from marginalized lands, this valorization seems less viable.

Three distinct “Closing” opportunities were identified and discussed in the context of the SOC. First, the **Oxygen-enriched stream from the SOC anode** has the potential to be fed back to the gasifier, reducing the need for an external oxygen supply. In practice, achieving the high purity required for direct use in Oxygen-blown gasification (>95–99% O₂) is technically challenging. When air is used on the (SOC) anode side for cooling, the resulting stream is Oxygen-enriched air (up to approximately 35% O₂) rather than pure Oxygen and a downstream separation step would be required. The resulting Nitrogen dilution from using oxygen-enriched air also increases the recirculation loads in the Methanol synthesis.

Second, the **high-temperature waste heat from the SOC** (operating at 600–800°C) **can be reused** via heat exchangers to pre-heat the inlet streams, improving overall system efficiency.

Third, the SOC requires high-purity water (demineralized, deionized) to generate steam. The condensed water downstream could be treated and recycled for this purpose, minimizing fresh water intake.

At the end-of-life, **material recycling is the most viable “Closing” pathway**, because the refurbishment of used stacks is not technically feasible, due to irreversible high-temperature material changes. Project partner ELCOGEN already recycles manufacturing scrap internally before sintering, and post-sintering scrap is returned to Nickel/Yttrium powder suppliers.

For complete decommissioned stacks, the steel can be magnetically separated and recycled conventionally; Nickel can be recovered via hydrometallurgical leaching processes; and the remaining ceramic fraction requires specialized separation processes. The primary barrier to economically viable end-of-life recycling is the scale. Dedicated recovery infrastructure requires consistent, high-volume feedstock streams at the gigawatt level, analogous to the evolution of lithium-ion battery recycling, which is currently not achievable for SOCs, but is a strategic consideration for long-term deployment.

The Methanol synthesis unit offers strong “Closing” potential for heat and materials. The exothermic reaction delivers substantial heat, and the 3D-printed **reactor is specifically designed to make this heat available for internal or external integration**. At full scale, the dynamic pinch-analysis simulations will optimize heat flows between the reactor, the gasifier, the SOC unit and the Methanol distillation stage. With respect to water, the Methanol synthesis process targets zero liquid discharge. The water separated during distillation is treated and recycled internally, with cooling water managed in a closed loop. For spent catalysts, interactions with commercial manufacturers indicate interest in receiving used material for research and analysis. At end-of-life, the high-value reactor alloy (Nickel-based or stainless steel) could be fully re-melted and reused as powder for additive manufacturing, effectively closing the material loop for the reactor housing, with no significant alloy degradation.

From a system perspective relating to all life cycle stages, the **plant location has a key influence on its industrial symbiosis**, and therefore, on **“Closing” potentials**. Ideally, the plant should be located in the proximity to biomass sources, to (process) heat users such as industrial facilities or district heating networks, and to partners that could valorize materials, especially biochar.

4.2.4. “Regenerate” strategies: Sourcing and valorizing regenerative resources

The “Regenerate” principle is foundational to the BeBOP concept as a whole. The BeBOP process is built around biomass as a low-Carbon feedstock, and renewable electricity as its energy source.

The workshop about biomass feedstocks confirmed that **clean wood remains the most viable and reliable biomass input** for large-scale deployment, at least in the near term. Forest residues and by-products from the wood industry offer additional regenerative potential with comparatively good predictability, while paper industry rejects were also highlighted as a secure secondary source. Feedstocks in the scope of BeBOP, such as Miscanthus grown on polluted soils for phytoremediation or post-used wood, have high sustainability value through the cascading of waste streams and the soil remediation benefits. A key strategic outcome from the workshop on feedstocks is that sustainability criteria and circularity value must be weighed against supply security and technical compatibility (due to ash contents, impurities, sizing variations, etc). with the gasification process If any of the latter risks applies, the downstream effects related to plant uptime and product revenues usually outweigh the price savings and sustainability benefits of secondary feedstocks.

For the SOC, the “Regenerate” principle is primarily expressed through **integration with renewable electricity** as the energy input. SOC stacks demonstrate good electrical load-following capability, making them well suited to coupling with intermittent wind or solar generation. However, the overall plant's ability to adapt to variable renewable supply depends on the flexibility of all integrated units. The initial BeBOP operation is expected to prioritize stable Methanol production over maximum renewable integration. Hydrogen buffer storage or electrical battery storage may be needed to smooth fluctuations from intermittent supply. The preferred solution might depend on the specific renewable energy profile.

The variable load operation of the Methanol synthesis reactor, achievable from 25 to 100% of design capacity with start-up and shutdown times of approximately one hour, is the key “regenerate” enabler, as it allows the synthesis unit to follow renewable electricity availability without requiring large-scale Hydrogen or syngas buffer storage. The lower bound of 25% operational capacity would enable electricity generation from the Syngas via SOFC mode, while a small portion of the Syngas is synthesized, avoiding a shutdown of the Methanol synthesis unit. The 3D-printed reactor's rapid thermal response, enabled by integrated heating elements and a lean structural design, is a technical advantage for this operational flexibility, and thus an effective way for the integration of renewable energy at the full plant level.

D4.2 - Validated strategies for ensuring sustainable circularity plans

From a system perspective, the **plants' location brings potential lever**: proximity to regional biomass sources would minimize transport-related emissions, while local agriculture would create the demand for soil amendments from biochar. As the SOC is a substantial user of electricity, proximity to excess renewable sources is also essential for a viable scaled-up process.

Circularity insights for the scaled-up BeBOP process				
CE Strategy	Feedstock Selection and Pre-treatment	Gasification and Cleaning	SOC	Methanol Synthesis
	Pre-treatment costs are typically higher with residue sources due to gasification requirements (size conformity and moisture content).	Potential for internal heat recuperation from gasification with gas reheating (before the SOC).	The primary SOC materials Nickel and Zirconium are currently irreplaceable.	3D-printed reactors can be scaled up by a combination of sizing and multiplication of units.
		Water from syngas condensation and cooling can be recycled and purified.	SOFC switching is highly flexible (in seconds), but downstream implications are partially a limiting factor.	Flexible operation is a key lever to allow for SOFC use and variable energy supply, while reducing the need for buffer storages.
	Impurities and ash content have a significant influence on downstream efficiency, plant uptime and component lifetime.	Gasifiers are generally non-modular, but still suitable for a range of feedstocks.	The target lifetime is 3 to 5 years, but uncertain and untested for co-electrolysis with Syngas.	The expected service life of the Methanol synthesis catalyst is 2-3 years
		Frequent shutdowns (and resulting temperature changes) are the main reason for gasifier degradation, shortening the lifespan of the refractory linings.	Gas purity is the most critical factor influencing the service life; tars and sulfur are primary degradation drivers.	The most important factors for catalyst service life are heat management and the purity of Syngas.
		Most important spare parts include filtering units, absorbents and catalysts for gas cleaning, gas sensors and high-wear seals.	The smallest replaceable units are stacks, which degrade heterogeneously dependent on location in the module.	Catalyst exchanges involve significant plant downtime due to the passivation process before removal and the reduction process before start-up.
	Using local biomass, providing jobs and allowing for heat integration (industry or district heating) have been proven in similar contexts to BeBOP.	Plant location should ideally be in proximity to both biomass sources and consumers of waste heat (industries or district heating).	Stack refurbishment is considered unfeasible due to the irreversibility of degradation.	Exothermic reaction provides heat which could be used internally for distillation downstream.
		Revalorization potential of ash and char is given in agriculture, but unclear at the moment.	Material recycling is feasible for steel, nickel and ceramics, if SOCs are sufficiently available.	Aiming for zero-water-discharge, means that the water from distillation will be reused internally.
		Used sorbents are typically recycled by the provider.	Recycled water must be of high purity and demineralized.	The reactors high-value alloy can be melted down and recycled into new printing powder.
	Feedstocks with predictable behavior (e.g., wood chips) remain the preferred choice due to operational security.	Bubbling fluidized bed gasifiers (BFB) allow for feedstock flexibility (e.g., woody biomass, RDFs, agricultural residues).	SOC stacks are theoretically capable of rapid electrical load-following, but limited by other factors: thermal management, gasifier and synthesis.	The reactor is designed for rapid load adaptation and short start-up and cool-down times of one hour, in order to allow for adaptability to renewable electricity generation.
		Trade-off between feedstock flexibility and overall efficiency and stability; cleaner, more uniform biomass performs better.		

Table 4. Circularity insights for the scaled-up BeBOP process.

4.3. From validated CE insights to quantitative Circularity Indicators

Workshop 5 focused on translating the qualitative circularity insights, validated in Workshops 1 to 4, into a quantitative framework of measurable Circularity Indicators.

The development process involved three key steps:

1. Identification of candidate indicators based on workshop discussions and circularity framework
2. Evaluation of indicators against criteria, including measurability, relevance to scale-up decisions, sensitivity to design choices and alignment with industry practice
3. Refinement of indicator definitions, including specification of measurement units, target values or directional aims and data sources.

The validated indicator set comprises 25 Circularity indicators specifically applied to and developed for the BeBOP process across its life cycle stages and organized according to the CE principles.

Table 5 presents the complete BeBOP Circularity Indicator Set developed during and after workshop 5. Each indicator is defined by its measurement unit, importance level (high, medium, low), in this way reflecting the workshop participants' prioritization and feasibility assessment (high, medium, low). High importance indicators are those expected to significantly influence system-level performance and/or represent relevant design optimization variables. Feasibility rating reflects practical considerations around measurement protocols, data availability and integration of such indicators with existing monitoring systems.

Selected indicators require a specific explanation. The SOC Stack Degradation Rate and Replacement Frequency are closely linked but measure different aspects: degradation rate captures gradual performance loss over time, while replacement frequency reflects the practical decision point when degradation makes continued operation uneconomic. Both are rated high importance, given the SOC's centrality to BeBOP economics and its sensitivity to operating conditions.

Heat Reuse or Integration Efficiency appears three times (Under gasification, SOC, Methanol synthesis) because the thermal integration opportunities and constraints differ substantially across these units. Within the gasification process, heat recovery is highly relevant due to the large thermal mass. Apart from the internal heat integration possibilities with the SOC operation and drying of feedstocks, this also allows for external use cases such as district heating. Similarly, the exothermic Methanol synthesis process also provides substantial waste heat for external use. The main difference is the lower temperature level. SOECs, on the other hand, are consumers of heat. For the SOEC mode, the objective is therefore to minimize heat losses wherever possible – this relates to the narrowing principles. In case the SOC is used in SOFC mode, the process is also exothermic and potentially available for external demand. In total, the amount of heat available for a scaled-up 100MW-biomass BeBOP plant for external use is estimated to be around 20MW (Rajaei et al. 2024).

The Secondary Source Index and Marginal Land Source Index both address feedstock sustainability but from different angles. Secondary sources include post-use materials and cascade utilization (e.g., construction wood after service life), reducing competition with virgin material uses. Marginal land biomass addresses land use pressure by utilizing degraded or contaminated lands unsuitable for food production. Both indicators face feasibility challenges around reliable data collection and verification of source claims.

CRM Recyclability Rate for SOC stacks received high importance rating reflecting stakeholder concern about critical material dependencies (nickel, zirconium) and strategic vulnerability. However, practical recycling pathways remain underdeveloped, contributing to medium-low feasibility assessment. This indicator may increase in feasibility as recycling value chains mature.

Circularity Indicators developed for the scaled-up BeBOP process												
CE Strategy	Feedstock Selection and Pre-treatment	I	F	Gasification and Cleaning	I	F	SOC	I	F	Methanol Synthesis	I	F
	Pre-treatment Energy Consumption Energy use for pre-treatment in kWh per kg of syngas	low	med	Cold Gas Efficiency chemical energy of syngas compared to feedstock	high	high	Specific Energy Consumption kWh/kg of hydrogen produced	high	high	Conversion Efficiency to Methanol % of carbon in conditioned syngas converted to methanol	high	high
	Feedstock Regionality average distance in km of feedstock transport	med	high				Heat Integration Efficiency % of heat recovered from the SOEC operation and utilized internally	high	high	Recycle Flow Rate % of unconverted syngas in the recycle flow / syngas input	high	high
	Feedstock Ash Content % of ash content by dry weight	high	high	Gasifier Uptime % of scheduled operational time the gasifier is performing to specification	high	high	SOC Stack Degradation Rate Average % loss in hydrogen production rate per 1000 operating hours	high	high	Catalyst Operational Lifetime Effective operation hours in relation to theoretical service life	med	high
	Feedstock Impurity Content Alkali Index, K and Na content in ash and Chlorine Content in % of weight	high	high	Maintenance Ratio Maintenance hours / 1000 operating hours per feedstock	low	med	SOC Stack Replacement Frequency % stack replacements/stack per 1000 hours	high	high	Reactor Maintenance Interval Maintenance hours / 1000 operating hours	med	high
	Secondary Source Index % of total feedstock input from secondary sources	high	med	Heat Reuse Efficiency % of heat recovered from the gasifier and utilized internally or externally	high	high	CRM Recyclability Rate % of CRMs in SOC stacks deemed recoverable with existing technologies	high	high	Heat Reuse Efficiency % of exothermic heat from MeOH synthesis utilized internally or externally	med	med
							Oxygen Utilization Rate % of oxygen produced by SOEC utilized vs. vented	med	high	Catalyst Material Circularity Rate % of catalyst material recovered and reprocessed from spent catalysts	low	med
							Water reuse efficiency % of water from MeOH distillation utilized internally or externally	low	med			
	Marginal Land Source Index % of total feedstock input from marginal lands	high	med	By-Product Valorization Rate % of gasifier ashes valorized from the total amount of ashes produced	high	med	Renewable Electricity Ratio for SOEC % of total electricity consumed by the SOEC sourced from renewable origins	high	high			

Table 5. Circularity Indicators developed for the scaled-up BeBOP process

4.4. Interdependencies of Circularity Indicators: Trade-offs and Synergies

The circularity indicators exhibit complex interdependencies - some indicators mutually reinforce each other (synergies) while others present inherent conflicts (trade-offs). Understanding these relationships is essential for optimization, as maximizing all indicators simultaneously is hardly feasible and counterproductive. This section presents the systematic analysis of indicator interdependencies conducted after the definition of Indicators. Table 6 provides a matrix representation of key indicator relationships. Positive values (+1, +2) indicate synergies, where improving one indicator tends to improve the other. Negative values (-1, -2) indicate trade-offs, where improving one indicator tends to worsen the other. The magnitude (1 vs. 2) reflects the strength of the relationship. Zero values indicate no significant direct relationship. The most significant trade-off relationships identified include:

- **Secondary Source Index vs. Gasifier Performance:** Increasing the proportion of secondary biomass sources (post-use wood, RDF, agricultural residues) enhances circularity from a regenerating perspective but introduces higher ash and impurity content. This directly impacts Cold Gas Efficiency (-2), Gasifier Uptime (-2) and Maintenance Ratio (-2). The relationship is strong because feedstock quality is a primary determinant of gasification performance.
- **Secondary Source Index vs. SOC Degradation:** Similarly, impurities from secondary sources that pass through gasification cleaning systems accelerate the SOC Stack Degradation Rate (-2) and increase Stack Replacement Frequency (-2). Even trace contaminants (ppb-level Sulphur) significantly impact the lifetime of the SOC, creating a tension between feedstock flexibility and component longevity.
- **Renewable Electricity Ratio vs. System Stability:** Maximizing renewable electricity use enhances the regenerating dimension but introduces variability that conflicts with component lifetime objectives. Frequent load changes and thermal cycling associated with intermittent renewable supply negatively impact SOC Stack Degradation Rate (-1), Gasifier Uptime (-1, due to thermal stress on refractories) and overall process efficiency. The magnitude is moderate (1) because technological solutions (thermal storage, flexible control) can partially mitigate impacts.

The main synergy relationships are:

- **Heat Reuse Efficiency (internal synergies):** Heat recovery from gasification enables Pre-treatment Energy Consumption reduction (+2), creating a direct synergy where waste heat from one unit displaces external energy for another. Similarly, SOEC waste heat can preheat inlet gases (+1) and methanol synthesis heat can support other thermal requirements (+1). These represent 'closing' synergies within narrowing objectives.
- **Feedstock Quality Synergies:** Low Feedstock Ash Content and Impurity Content mutually reinforce (+2) Cold Gas Efficiency, Gasifier Uptime, SOEC Degradation Rate and Catalyst Operational Lifetime. This cluster of synergies reflects that feedstock quality improvements yield benefits throughout the value chain. However, these synergies exist in tension with Secondary Source Index objectives.
- **Oxygen Utilization Rate and Cold Gas Efficiency:** Utilizing SOEC oxygen output to support gasification (rather than venting) enhances both closing objectives (material loop) and narrowing objectives (reduced external oxygen requirement). The synergy magnitude is moderate (+1) as implementation requires oxygen enrichment or separation infrastructure.

The implications derived from this analysis are further discussed in the Outlook, specifically chapter 5.1 Recommendations for BeBOP scale-ups.

			Feedstock Selection and Pretreatment					Gasification and Cleaning					SOC					Methanol Synthesis										
		Influence of ↓ on →	Pretreatment Energy Consumption	Feedstock Regionality	Feedstock Ash Content	Feedstock Impurity Content	Secondary Source Index	Marginal Land Source Index	Cold Gas Efficiency	Gasifier Uptime	Maintenance Ratio (Gasifier)	Heat Reuse Efficiency (Gasifier)	By-Product Valorization Rate	Specific Energy Consumption (SOEC)	SOEC Stack Degradation Rate	SOEC Stack Replacement Frequency	Heat Reuse Efficiency (SOEC)	CRM Recyclability Rate	Oxygen Utilization Rate	Renewable Electricity Ratio for SOEC	Conversion Efficiency for Methanol	Recycle Flow Rate	Catalyst Operation Lifetime	Reactor Maintenance Interval	Heat Reuse Efficiency (MeOH unit)	Catalyst Material Circularity Rate	Water Reuse Efficiency	
		Value aimed to be .. to improve circularity																										
Feedstock Selection and Pretreatment	Pretreatment Energy Consumption	low			-1	-2				-2	-2																	
	Feedstock Regionality	low																										
	Feedstock Ash Content	low							1	2	2												2	1				
	Feedstock Impurity Content	low							1	2	2												2	1				
	Secondary Source Index	high			-2	-2			-1	-2	-2														-2			
	Marginal Land Source Index	high			-2	-2			-1	-2	-2														-2			
Gasification and Cleaning	Cold Gas Efficiency	high																			1							
	Gasifier Uptime	high																										
	Maintenance Ratio (Gasifier)	low																										
	Heat Reuse Efficiency (Gasifier)	high	2								-1	-1		1														
	By-Product Valorization Rate	high																										
	SOC	Specific Energy Consumption (SOEC)	low																									
SOEC Stack Degradation Rate		low												2		2												
SOEC Stack Replacement Frequency		low																										
Heat Reuse Efficiency (SOEC)		high	2								-1	-1		1														
CRM Recyclability Rate		high																										
Oxygen Utilization Rate		high							2					1														
Renewable Electricity Ratio for SOEC		high																										
Methanol Synthesis	Conversion Efficiency for Methanol	high																										
	Recycle Flow Rate	low																				2						
	Catalyst Operation Lifetime	high																										
	Reactor Maintenance Interval	low																										
	Heat Reuse Efficiency (MeOH unit)	high	2								-1	-1		1														
	Catalyst Material Circularity Rate	high																										
	Water Reuse Efficiency	high																										

Table 6. Interdependency of Circularity Indicators

4.5. Identifying circular business model opportunities

4.5.1. The role of business models in realizing circularity potentials

While Workshops 1-4 identified technical circularity strategies and Workshop 5 translated these into quantitative indicators, Workshop 6 addressed the crucial question of how circular economy principles can be embedded in business models that enable and incentivize circularity. The theoretical circularity potential remains unrealized without appropriate value capture mechanisms.

Circular business models (CBMs) differ from traditional linear models in several fundamental ways. Rather than one-time product sales, CBMs often emphasize service provision, performance guarantees and long-term relationships that align incentives for producers to maximize product longevity and resource efficiency. For capital-intensive technologies like BeBOP, CBMs can address key barriers, including high upfront investment requirements and technological uncertainty and split incentives between equipment manufacturers and plant operators.

To guide the process of circular business model development, the framework “Make it Circular: A gamified introduction to circular business models” was applied. The methodology was developed by the Circular Economy Initiative Germany and provides a structured process to identify circular opportunities in a range of resource-intensive sectors. The game guides participants through a series of card decks to identify concrete circular model opportunities and apply them step by step to a given business model – see also one of the final developed game boards from the workshop in Figure 2. The process is explained in detail in the workshop summary report and on the website of the game developers.² The methodology requires a certain perspective and role to be predefined in case there is no “linear” business model to vantage from. For that purpose, two contrasting scenarios were developed for the first small-scale deployment phase around 2030:

- 'Plug and Play Methanol' emphasizing distributed, modular upgrades of gasification infrastructure with standardized components
- 'The Eternal SOC' focusing on component longevity through maintenance and repair services

Two independent groups worked on the Plug and Play scenario, one group on the eternal SOC scenario. The following chapters focus on the main insights that were gained in each scenario analysis (§4.5.2 and §4.5.3) and what general enablers and barriers for the future implementations of CBMs for BeBOP can be derived from that (§4.5.4).

² See: <https://www.circular-economy-initiative.de/make-it-circular-a-gamified-introduction-to-circular-business-models-in-a-corporate-setting>

Figure 2. Developed "Make it Circular"-Gameboard for "The Eternal SOEC"-Group

4.5.2. Scenario analysis: "Plug and play methanol"

Scenario 1: "Plug and Play" Methanol	
Background	This scenario focused on the potential revitalization of the 8MW Dual Fluidized Bed (DFB) gasifier in Güssing, Austria, which was shut down in 2016 for economic reasons. The site possesses key advantages, including good local woody biomass availability and access to cheap renewable electricity
Role	Supplier of BeBOP Technology
Product	An integrated SOC + Methanol Synthesis upgrade package
Value Proposition	Enhancing the value of an existing, dormant gasifier infrastructure.
Question to be addressed	How can the "Plug and Play Methanol" package be framed as a circular business model that revitalizes the closed Güssing plant by leveraging its existing infrastructure and local advantages (biomass and renewable electricity) to create new revenue streams?

Table 7. Scenario Definition for the "Plug and Play" Scenario

The discussions around the "Plug and Play Methanol" scenario (see Table 7) converged on a clear insight for a first-of-a-kind employment of BeBOP technology: simply selling the hardware to a customer carries significant reputational risk. If the plant is misoperated or underperforms, the technology itself is likely to be blamed. This would undermine prospects for future market uptake. This reasoning favored the selection of a service-oriented model in which the technology provider retains operational control and responsibility for performance, with the customer paying for the result - for example per tonne of methanol produced - rather than for the physical asset. This arrangement would make the technology more attractive for the customer, while giving the supplier of BeBOP technology the control needed to ensure, that the installation functions as a successful reference demonstrator. Both groups working on this scenario independently arrived at this conclusion.

In terms of implementation, the key mechanism discussed was a revenue-sharing arrangement between the technology supplier and the plant operator: the operator receives an increasing share of revenues above a defined production threshold. This incentive structure was designed to align both parties around the principle of maximizing plant uptime. The partnerships required to make this model viable extend well beyond the supplier and operator: a financial investor willing to fund the upfront capital, a long-term methanol off-taker, the gasifier infrastructure owner, biomass and electricity suppliers and specialized maintenance partners were all identified as critical for the value chain. The precise financial and contractual definition of such a model - including pricing mechanisms, risk allocation and operational responsibilities - remains an important open question to be addressed in subsequent project work (WP11, T11.3 Final business cases and models).

4.5.3. Scenario analysis: “The eternal SOEC”

Scenario 2: “The Eternal SOC”	
Background	<i>This scenario focused on a new-build project, the planned 8MW Biomass-to-X plant in Zeltweg, Austria, by Advanced Bioenergy Lab (ABL). The plant will use forestry waste to produce alcohols from secondary woody biomass.</i>
Role	SOC Producer
Product	A flexible SOEC / SOFC system
Value Proposition	Increasing the Carbon efficiency and operational flexibility of the new biomass-to-X process (e.g., switching between electrolysis and fuel cell mode).
Question to be addressed	How can the SOEC usage time be maximized by addressing lifetime influences while balancing the needs of the plant operator (ABL Zeltweg) and the technology expert (SOEC supplier) in a circular business model?

Table 8. Scenario Definition for "The Eternal SOEC" Scenario

The "Eternal SOEC" scenario (Table 8) centered on how a SOEC producer can structure its offering in a way that maximizes the useful lifetime of the technology while remaining financially viable for both parties. From the customer perspective it was recognized that the best model would be one where the producer guarantees performance, maintenance and replacement. However, this would also place an unrealistically high financial burden on the producer of a nascent technology.

A leasing model was therefore identified as a more pragmatic near-term approach: the producer retains ownership of the SOC system throughout its service life and charges the operator a periodic fee, while also taking the unit back at end of life. This arrangement preserves the producer's access to the valuable materials within the decommissioned stacks (such as rare earth elements, nickel and steel). This was also identified as an important economic opportunity, since a material recycling route would also lower the producer's overall cost base.

Such a model requires a substantially different partner structure than a conventional equipment sales model. Access to upfront financing was identified as the most critical dependency, given that assets must be built before lease revenues begin to flow. Logistics for take-back, refurbishment subcontractors and a specialized recycling partner for end-of-life stack processing were also highlighted as essential for the value chain. The group saw this leasing approach as a realistic market-entry position, with the option to move towards more comprehensive service models as the technology gains operational know-how and market confidence grows.

4.5.4. Key enablers and barriers for CBM implementation

The workshop brought a set of enabling conditions and challenges relevant to both scenarios into view.

In terms of **enablers**, certain design and digital characteristics of the technology appeared to be prerequisites for service-oriented model. A **modular architecture** was seen as fundamental. This would allow individual units to be replaced or scaled without taking the whole system offline.

D4.2 - Validated strategies for ensuring sustainable circularity plans

Designing for **ease of maintenance and disassembly** matters equally. **Remote monitoring**, enabling the provider to track system health and predict maintenance needs from a distance, was identified as a practical necessity for any leasing or performance-based arrangement. There is also potential in using operational data to run the system at lower-efficiency conditions, deliberately trading some short-term output for a longer service life.

The **barriers** should not be underestimated. Service-oriented and leasing models require **significant upfront capital** before revenues begin to flow. This is a particular challenge for a technology that is not yet widely proven commercially. These models also demand **organizational capabilities in operations, take-back logistics and partner management** - that differ considerably from those of a conventional "asset" business. Supply chain dependencies across financing, logistics, repair and recycling add further complexity. The **absence of established standards** for refurbished components introduces additional uncertainty. None of these barriers are necessarily insurmountable, but they suggest that the transition to more ambitious circular business models beyond leasing (such as purely performance-based contracts) will likely be gradual.

5. Outlook: Ensuring sustainable circularity plans

5.1. Recommendations for BeBOP scale-ups

Based on the comprehensive work done in WP4, several key recommendations emerge for BeBOP technology scale-up:

- **Design for SOC longevity**
The SOC stack is the critical variable for both economic viability and circularity performance. Every design and operational decision that extends stack lifetime has disproportionately large impact. There is also a potential trade-off with narrowing, by sacrificing efficiency by running the SOEC with lower temperatures to maximize life time of stacks. The modular design of assemblies enabling the exchange of stacks is important not only due to the heterogenous degradation mechanism of SOC stacks. It would also ease the realization of any service-oriented business model.
- **Build heat integration into the plant concept**
Internal heat recovery is the obvious closing lever in the BeBOP process and carries few negative trade-offs. Surplus heat (~20 MW in a 100 MW scale-up) is also available for external valorization, representing an additional revenue stream. BeBOP therefore has the chance to not only substitute fossil-based methanol but also fossil-based heat, dependent on the location and demand at the plant site.
- **Choose plant location strategically to maximize Industrial Symbiosis**
The plant location is probably the most consequential circularity lever available to BeBOP. A well-chosen location in the planning stage can simultaneously realize closing, regenerating and narrowing benefits: proximity to regional biomass sources reduces transport emissions and supports a reliable feedstock supply. Co-location with industrial heat consumers or district heating networks enables surplus process heat to be valorized externally. Access to local residue streams – preferably from the forestry or wood processing industries - opens pathways for industrial symbiosis that strengthen both the regenerative and closing dimensions of the plant's circularity profile. Proximity to renewable electricity generation reduces the cost and Carbon intensity of SOEC operation. Location decisions should therefore be evaluated against all of these dimensions early in the deployment process.
- **Prioritize feedstock quality as a system-wide circularity lever**
Feedstock selection is the single most consequential upstream choice affecting the circularity performance of the entire process. Clean, sustainably sourced woody biomass maximizes efficiency and protects the lifetimes of downstream components. Secondary and residue-based feedstocks would be generally preferable from the perspective of cascading a scarce resource with increased usage competition, but inherent impurities were often seen as a significant risk for plant uptime and the service life of components. WP2 and WP3 will provide more clarity from test runs of the pilot plant, regarding the performance of secondary feedstocks.
- **Plan for material loops**
For solid waste streams, valorization routes for biochar and ash from clean biomass sources are established, but also depend on the impurity levels that vary with feedstock choice. This makes waste stream management and feedstock strategy inseparable. For the SOC, material recycling at the end of life is technically feasible but currently requires large deployment volumes to be economically viable. Due to the high value and the short life time of SOC stacks, business models where these are taken back should be prioritized (WP11).
- **Adopt a service-oriented commercial model for initial deployments**
The business model analysis indicated that circular opportunities are best realized through models in which the technology provider retains responsibility for performance. For the

integrated plant, a performance-based revenue-sharing arrangement was independently endorsed by multiple stakeholder groups as the most appropriate approach for a first-of-a-kind deployment. For SOEC supply, a leasing model was seen as a more pragmatic near-term entry point. Both approaches align commercial incentives with CE goals. Developing concrete service level agreements and financial models for both scenarios is the logical next step, as direct input to the exploitation work of WP11.

- **Use the interdependencies between CE principles as a planning tool**

BeBOP's circularity cannot be optimized one dimension at a time. The most important tension to manage is between feedstock flexibility and process stability. The indicator framework and trade-off matrix are designed to make these relationships visible. WP5 and WP6 will make use of the indicators and the identified trade-offs to design application scenarios accordingly.

5.2. Limitations and integration of results in upcoming WPs

Several limitations of this circularity assessment should be acknowledged. The workshop-based methodology relies on expert judgment and qualitative discussions. As BeBOP pilot plant demonstration progresses, empirical data will enable validation and refinement of the indicators and their trade-off relationships.

Economic dimensions of circularity (costs, revenue opportunities, investment requirements) have been discussed but not systematically quantified. Some circularity interventions (heat integration, feedstock flexibility) have clear economic benefits, while others (component refurbishment, secondary material recovery) require detailed cost-benefit analysis to establish viability. The techno-economic analysis (WP5-6) will partly assess whether circularity strategies are economically viable.

The indicator framework focuses on production-side metrics without directly addressing demand-side considerations such as methanol end-use patterns or Carbon storage in chemical products. These broader system-level considerations will be addressed in the system analysis work (WP5-6), especially the LCA. Furthermore, the LCA aims to analyze how circularity strategies perform in different impact categories.

The indicators, the interdependency analysis and especially the insights gained from the scenario analysis should provide a framework to define a viable business model for the exploitation plan within WP11.

5.3. Further Integration of stakeholders in the Project

As mentioned in Chapter 3.3, the involvement of Advisory Board and Stakeholders' Network members will continue beyond the formal completion of WP4 activities, integrating their involvement not only for periodic consultations but also within dissemination, exploitation and clustering activities. Future engagement will focus on maintaining active dialogue (and mapping feedback and interests) through targeted workshops/events, cross-project collaborations and participation in external networks and initiatives.

Some actions are already planned for the next reporting period to complement and boost ongoing engagement such as: **i.** a parallel session of BeBOP at the European Biomass Conference and Exhibition (EUBCE) where BeBOP aims to further validate its concepts through dialogue with the broader bio-based industry ecosystem; **ii.** a joint symposium co-organized with other 6 EU-funded projects, including [Flexby](#); [Fuel-Up](#); [TEAPOTS](#); [Fuels-C](#); [PYSOLO](#); [Bio-MeGaFuel](#) aimed at fostering a valuable discussion on sustainability assessment, product standardization and the deployment of next-generation biofuel pathways; and **iii.** dedicated event in collaboration with the Methanol Institute.

Further integration will also be supported through clustering activities with related EU-funded projects (Hubs4Circularity ecosystem with a focus on UNITED CIRCELS) and through participation in European Commission support services, such as the Horizon Results Booster (ongoing). Stakeholder inputs will continue to inform business model development, market positioning strategies and replication scenarios, ensuring that technical outcomes remain aligned with industrial expectations and regulatory developments.

Through this continuous engagement, BeBOP aims at supporting industrial uptake and positioning of the BeBOP project in the EU circular bio-economy scenario.

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